

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries:
Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

1. Overview

This proposal seeks funding to convene, engage, and co-develop a critically-needed, low-tech, and sustainable framework for data sharing leading practices with three geoscience disciplines: hydrology, oceans, and seismology. The goal is to empower these target disciplines to be knowledgeable of, and connected to, their community's existing CI resources, technologies and leading practices; proactive in effectively and efficiently managing and sharing FAIR research outputs (Wilkinson et. al., 2016). The impact will result in higher quality, interoperable data being shared through community-preferred disciplinary repositories, accessible for immediate reuse in data-driven research, including AI/ML applications. For this proposal, the term 'data' refers to research data, software, physical samples, images, video, and other digital objects related to research.

Through this work, we will convene necessary disciplinary stakeholders (researchers, repositories, journal editors, research infrastructure) to **co-identify, aggregate, and organize currently disparate, dark, or misaligned community-specific resources, such as appropriate repositories, funder, and publisher guidance, data reporting and sharing resources, standards, and leading practices.** We will create a centralized web platform for discovering and accessing these resources that can provide the activation energy necessary to infuse FAIR and Open Data and Science practices into current research workflows.

The three target disciplines have been selected based on their receptiveness to engage on FAIR data and Open Science topics in addition to the existence of supporting community resources such as repositories, vocabularies, published practices, and strong, engaged society membership. The process will be researcher-driven, involving co-creation of a framework that will be community-vetted and endorsed. Sustainability will be ensured through adoption and ongoing management of the framework by community stakeholders such as AGU and EGU disciplinary sections and divisions. A Framework Toolkit, derived from the synthesized experiences from engaging with the three target disciplines, will serve as a template for additional disciplines demonstrating community readiness.

This work will advance FAIR data management and Open Science, integrating these practices into existing research lifecycles moving toward an Open Science Ecosystem, evolving scientific habits and norms. The impact of this will improve the quality and reusability of publicly-accessible data, facilitating robust research and education that would otherwise not occur; including the use of emerging data-driven AI and ML techniques that require high-quality interoperable data to solve complex Earth system challenges. These outcomes ultimately expand the benefit of NSF research investments (NSF 23-131, 2023). **Project Outcomes Include:**

For Hydrology, Oceans, and Seismology:

1. A Discipline-Specific (e.g., community-specific) Data and Digital Object Management Framework, containing a vetted set of leading practices that are reviewed, approved, and mapped to the framework.
2. A neutrally-branded web platform where community members can easily locate trusted data and digital object management leading practices with the context to apply the information.
3. Engaged Discipline Leadership, Discipline Liaisons, and researchers that support and use the vetted resources, monitor for new leading practices, and sustain the framework with updated content.

Tool Kit: Framework Toolkit, with implementation guidance, for additional disciplines to implement that are demonstrating community readiness.

Open Science Definition: For the purpose of this work we align with the UNESCO Open Science Recommendations where: Open science is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefits of scientists and society as a whole. Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is accessible to all and sustainable (UNESCO, 2022). The UNESCO Recommendation provides an internationally agreed definition, as well as a set of actions conducive to [fair] operationalization of open science for all at the individual, institutional, national, regional and international levels. In this proposal we target the discipline-specific Open Science practices for data, using our broad definition, and working openly as a team.

2. Introduction and Background: Evolution of the Status Quo: Public Access of research data fuels new scientific discoveries and insights, supports education and contributes to government policy, resource management and global sustainability goals. In an effort to maximize the investment made in nationally- and internationally-funded research data, funder and governmental policies direct researchers to share their research output (e.g., NSF 23-104, NSF 23-018, NSF 20-068, NSF 19-069, Holdren Memo 2013, Nelson Memo 2022, Department of Education, Skills and Employment (2022), European Council Data Act, 2023). Researchers face a complex landscape of conflicting national, funder, institutional, and publisher policies, guidelines, and mandates. Further, the value and incentives around sharing research data are not rooted enough to motivate a research team to build in the effort to prepare these items throughout their current research lifecycle. Though requirements have been placed on researchers directing them to follow their “community-specific standards and open science principles” (NSF EAR Data Management and Sharing Plan Guidance, July 2023), such community-specific guidance does not exist in the geosciences in a consolidated, discoverable and vetted manner. With thorough review of literature it would be possible to find elements of what would constitute leading practices for community-specific data sharing, but it is unlikely that a researcher would recognize any particular recommended practice as being endorsed by their community and thus the proper protocol to integrate with their research lifecycle. They therefore spend valuable research time navigating this uncertain landscape.

In the absence of clear community-centric guidance, data are being shared through generalist repositories where there is no support for documentation that provides the context for the creation and use of that data. In 2024, 80% of all AGU papers have a data (or software) citation where 75% of those citations are from a generalist repository (Fig. 3). In short, the explicit requirement to share data has been met, but the value of supporting the research findings and potential reuse, and to “stand on the shoulders of giants” (Newton, 1675) is not achieved. Without proper preservation and sharing, the value of the data as a research product output is lost, thereby **failing to ever realize its investment potential**. When summed over the total investment in scientific research, this loss grows to staggering proportions. Further, current data discovery practices for many geoscience disciplines are to survey the literature and manually identify the data relevant to the goals of the researcher. This is incredibly time consuming. Potential AI tools to do this work require the AI models to be trained on what “good” data and “bad” data look like, and it is becoming widely accepted that AI tools need to be data-driven (Maskey, 2023) using large amounts of well-documented, well-prepared data. However, achieving this state is hindered by the lack of use of scientific repositories that are FAIR-aligned, and follow discipline-specific standards and open science principles. The **loss of efficiency** when a discipline’s community does not support and endorse one or more FAIR-aligned repositories for both contributing data, *and* having the benefit of reusing the data deposited by others and curated to a standard protocol, drastically impacts the “time to science”.

3. Introducing the Concept: Achieving a more effective and Open Science research workflow requires a perspective that acknowledges the needs of the data depositor as well as the potential reuser of the data. Work by Yakel et. al (2024) identified ‘data reuser trust’ dimensions that include learning the values of your discipline community and enacting those values. Additionally, the ‘trust relationship’ between the discipline community and the disciplinary repository is described as being complex but necessary to develop and nurture to have the best possible understanding and support for data reuse. Faniel et al. (2010, 2017, 2019) further highlights the importance of research community perceptions on the data

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

source and available context information to help trust and understand the data. Nusser et al. (2021) found that when researchers are **transparent**, publishing their findings to include sharing data that is carefully prepared, well-documented, and able to withstand public scrutiny, there is higher trust in the research findings and of the supporting data. This is reinforced in AGU's publications with a higher citation rate for papers that cite data in the Reference Section (Vrouwenvelder & Platt, 2024). The context information (Faniel et al., 2019), along with topics to consider when sharing data for transparency (Nusser et al., 2021), as well as the role of repositories and data reuser trust (Yakel et al., 2024) are best explored by a discipline community with all stakeholders of the research lifecycle are present.

The proposers, along with key collaborators described below and organizations represented in the Letters of Collaboration, are uniquely positioned to co-convene transformative discipline-specific workshops that result in the identification and vetting of data, software, and other digital object leading practices for hydrology, oceans, and seismology. This collaborative work will result in a Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Management Framework. **The objective is for each discipline to define their community-specific standards and leading practices and sustain their value to their researchers through review and update for new methods, tools, resources.**

4. Digging into the Status Quo: Current Practices and Challenges: Below we summarize the current realities of data sharing as they relate to three key stakeholders: (1) researchers, (2) data repositories, (3) journal editors and publishers. We conclude with a synthesis of the collective impact of these realities on science. The proposed discipline-specific framework will not only be a resource for researchers but will also serve as a valuable compendium providing added benefit to support journal editors, and inform repositories direction for both short- and long-term standards adoption and community interoperability goals as well as information they can provide to support disciplinary data submitters.

4.1 Researcher Perspective

Disciplinary Practice Status Quo: Researchers have a concept of the use of author ORCID and funder/journal-required data sharing in repositories; they face generalized data management and data management plan (DMP) expectations with no explicit guidance tailored to their disciplinary needs.

Once research data are created, they are typically organized, and quality controlled for analysis. After analysis, the research workflow typically progresses to drafting a resultant manuscript for publication. In general, the act of sharing the data that underpin the manuscript is often put off, driven by the concern that it may be used by others before a researcher has a chance to use it themselves, thereby getting "scooped" (Digital Science et al., 2019). Oftentimes, a researcher will request an embargo period for their data from the funding agency until they are ready to publish their findings. Embargo prohibits public access to the data for a period of time (2 years indicated by NSF 23-131; 1 year indicated in the Nelson Memo 2022) to provide the researcher ample time to analyze and develop their manuscript, essentially putting the curation process "on hold". This ability, in addition to the fear of being 'scooped' has a negative consequence of delaying the moment in time a researcher begins working with a repository and/or preparing their data for sharing.

Once researchers submit their manuscript to a journal that requires data sharing from a repository, they must prepare and deposit their data in a repository and obtain a persistent identifier (PIDs), specifically a DOI (Digital Object Identifier). This data submission requirement and the fact that it will stop the publication from advancing to peer review often comes as a surprise to an author. This places pressure on the author/researcher to deposit and obtain a DOI for the data quickly, via the path of least resistance.

Researchers also delay working with a repository early because of concern that requests to revise data may occur during the manuscript peer review process and are unaware of how these requests would be resolved if the data are already preserved. Complicating this is the fact that some discipline repositories, under their funding requirements, request the full corpus of project data for curation even though only a

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

small subset may be published in the manuscript, adding additional time for the author to obtain the DOI for the data.

Journal requirements for data sharing have evolved rapidly over the past 10-15 years (Data Citation Synthesis Group, 2014; Nosek et al., 2015; Stall et al., 2019). These journal requirements often represent unexpected and unplanned effort for researchers. Additionally, this requirement to share data often comes under the compressed time scales of the journal publication process, instilling a sense of urgency in the researcher to solve their data sharing and DOI dilemma quickly. When researchers share data in a repository and include a proper citation in their paper, the data cited are what is necessary to support the research findings. This is now the norm for publication, and reinforced by most funder requirements. In these cases, a generalist repository is commonly chosen, as noted by AGU journals demonstrating that 75% of all data citations are with generalist repositories (Fig. 3).

4.2 Repository Perspective

Disciplinary Guidance Status Quo: Repository guidance for researchers spans a spectrum from providing little or none, to highly detailed; there is a desire to work with researchers during the research lifecycle, but no incentives or mechanisms for sustaining that engagement with their community users. With limited funding/capacity to support researchers, most engagement is “ad hoc”, typically driven by publication crises or confusion.

Numerous data repositories exist within the geosciences to receive, manage, and publish output from scientific research (i.e., data, code and software, and related information). Broadly, these infrastructures

Figure 2. Schematic showing FAIR principles most often fulfilled by disciplinary vs. generalist repositories. After Lehnert & Hsu (2015).

comprise two types: those that serve specific disciplines with services tailored to their community’s disciplinary needs, and those that are generalist, accepting data from a wide array of scientific disciplines (Lin, 2024). Disciplinary repositories typically perform specialized curation, employ community standards and leading practices that meet FAIR Data Principles, and tend to have strong connections to their research communities (Fig. 2). Generalist repositories capture minimal metadata, lack the specialized services and technologies to make the data they archive align with the FAIR Principles, and service many scientific disciplines with minimal connection to individual communities as noted in NIH’s Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) (NIH, 2022). Data that are not ‘science-ready’ consume up to 80% of researcher time in wrangling, cleaning, and making interoperable (Hodson & Gregory, 2024). Economic analysis, funded by the European Commission, estimates the opportunity cost of not having data that support FAIR Data Principles to be 10.2B per annum (European Commission, 2018).

Both types of repositories are capable of data publishing and obtaining DOIs that may then be provided to journal editors for use in peer review and citation in the related manuscript.

Funders recognizing the distinction and value gained through disciplinary curation, have invested in the creation of disciplinary repository infrastructure (e.g., NSF-supported repositories: BCO-DMO, EarthChem, SESAR, CCHDO, MagIC, NCAR Research Data Archive, PlanetMicrobe, R2R, NDSF, GAGE, SAGE) and encourage or require awardees to leverage these repositories for data sharing,

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

whenever possible (EAR Data Management and Sharing Plan Guidance, 2023, NSF OCE Sample and Data Policy, 2024). However, the curation process of a disciplinary repository requires time to create high-quality, well-described published datasets. In comparison, a generalist repository that does not perform discipline-specific curation can publish a deposited dataset and provide a dataset DOI in a very short time frame. In disciplinary repositories, curation of a dataset precedes the registration to get a DOI assigned. This often creates problems for researchers who submit their manuscript to a journal prior to reaching out to a repository to share their data, as they will need to provide data access and a dataset DOI quickly for peer review and final publication. This situation creates a sense of urgency on behalf of the researcher to find a solution that will rapidly provide dataset access and DOI necessary for the scholarly publication process.

4.3 Journal Editor Perspective:

Disciplinary Practice Status Quo: Journal editors have limited information on community leading practices specific to preferred repositories. As their only option, they reference the repositories previously used by authors, which reinforces the use of generalist repositories (AGU, 2021). Data receive the necessary context information for reuse when shared in a disciplinary repository.

Most publishers follow a common workflow process to optimize operations, using automation to lower costs. Mandates as noted above from the US and other countries have helped drive journals to update author guidelines to require data citation in the References Section and a description of the data supporting the findings in the Data Availability Statement (DAS) (Enabling FAIR Data Community, 2018). Journal editors commonly do not require a specific repository be used, just that it provides a DOI to support a proper data citation. Some publishers incorporate generalist repositories into their workflow, e.g., Elsevier uses Mendeley Data; Springer Nature uses Figshare. This is primarily done to keep barriers to publication low, manage peer review and confidential access to the data, and control publication workflow at high manuscript submission rates (e.g., hundreds or thousands per day). However, these

Figure 3. Top 10 repositories used in primary research papers published in AGU journals in 2022. Modified from Vrouwenvelder & Stall (2024).

repositories do not support discipline-specific documentation and curation, i.e., data may or may not follow community leading practices with required context information nor provide the authors with curation support. When discipline-specific repositories are used by authors, they require additional time to complete curation processes. The coordination of timelines requires manual intervention, and the editor and staff time necessary equates to higher costs to the publisher and impacts manuscript turnaround times. It is important to emphasize that journals are motivated by a dataset having a DOI over data that is compliant with the FAIR principles that support interoperability and reusability.

Beginning in 2019, AGU's journals implemented the *Enabling FAIR Data* recommended author guidelines requiring data supporting the findings in the paper be both described in the DAS and cited in the References Section. In 2024, 80% of all AGU papers cited at least one dataset or software. However, over 75% of these citations are from generalist repositories (Figure 3) supporting transparency, but not the context necessary for reuse.

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

The journal has the responsibility to ensure funder mandates are followed as best they can. Without communities, such as AGU Sections, intervening to ensure that data management is integrated through the research lifecycle, the poor timing for considering data management at the very last moment - the time of research findings publication -- results in:

- 1) authors having a strong sense of urgency to “get a DOI” quickly (or ‘fast DOI’) for the data (or other digital object) with little or no consideration of ensuring the data/digital object is understandable and reusable -- making it a valuable scientific contribution.
- 2) journal editors with limited information on community leading practices specific to preferred repositories. As their only option, they reference the repositories previously used by authors, which reinforces the use of generalist repositories (AGU, 2021).

In short, for data to have the context information that will instill trust by those interested in transparency or reuse, the time to consider data management and sharing starts at research project inception and through the entire research lifecycle.

5. Risks of Maintaining Status Quo

Non-vetted Discipline-Specific Practices (Researcher, Repository): The lack of a community resource for managing data standards and leading practices blocks researchers from finding all available data relevant to their scientific research question. Today, **when data are difficult to find or seemingly do not exist, the intended research question is often reframed to move forward with just data that can be found and examined.** It is difficult to determine the number of times researchers are forced to adjust their hypothesis to better accommodate the data they were able to locate and wrangle into something usable by their software and APIs. **How much research is not being done under these limiting circumstances?** Discipline-specific guidance would encourage use of preferred repositories that conform to standards that enable FAIR data and provide a clear understanding of what data truly does exist, reducing the issue of data being in repositories that do not support online discovery, or worse still, not shared at all. With trusted, identified community resources, the question of “where is the data” begins to dissipate quickly.

Misaligned Workflow (Researcher, Repository, Journal Editor): The mismatch in timelines for researcher engagement with repositories, specific to the time needed for data curation, and journal peer review processes, coupled with the lack of discipline-specific community guidance, causes friction among the relevant stakeholders. The current compartmentalization of these stakeholder activities results in little or no communication among them to address emerging problems.

If a researcher has not worked with a repository to share their data prior to submitting their manuscript, journal requirements will likely become the paramount driver for where and how to share. The faster the paper is published, the faster the authors meet their primary goals. Disciplinary repository curation can be anywhere between 2-6 weeks and sometimes longer.

This discontinuity compromises the integrity of the published research. Citing the supporting data without critical community-specific metadata and vocabularies threatens effective reuse for future research and is only valuable for limited transparency to the publication. Other negative consequences include: non-compliance with funder requirements that may result in required corrective actions; loss of the opportunity to create fully FAIR-compliant data that maximizes federal investment in research and repositories (e.g., NSF 23-104; European Commission, 2018; The National Science and Technology Council, 2022); and data that may subsequently require duplicative curation by a disciplinary repository, costing money and effort.

Misaligned Incentives (Researcher): With no vetted guidance available to researchers on what data needs to be shared, where, and when, there is no incentive for an author to alter current behavior to plan for the resources and time prior to submitting their manuscript.

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries:
Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

Summary: Taken together, these circumstances result in suboptimal data sharing practices that are orthogonal to the tenets of Open Science and FAIR Data and ultimately impact the amount of FAIR data being properly curated and provisioned for reuse. In brief, the risk of not doing the work described in the proposal are:

Risk 1: Valuable data continues to circumvent sharing through a FAIR-aligned repository preferred by the community.

Risk 2: Researchers continue to use the ‘fast DOI’ approach for citing data that complies with journal guidance, but does not support **trusted** discovery, understanding, interoperability, or reuse.

The magnitude of the issue with ‘fast DOIs’ can be seen in AGU journals as noted in Figure 3. 60% of AGU papers in 2024 have a data citation using a ‘fast DOI’. This scenario is non-unique to any specific geoscience discipline and appears to be happening globally (Hahnel, 2022). This proposed work is fundamental in forging pathways to FAIR data. Equally important is the downstream impact of provisioning FAIR data that are necessary for responsible, data-driven, AI practices and applications (Maskey, 2023).

6. Beyond the Status Quo: The Time is Right for Three Target Disciplinary Communities

We have selected three disciplines that are primed for ignition towards adoption of a Discipline-Specific Data and Software Management Framework. Below is an overview of the rationale for selecting these disciplines based on their community readiness to co-assess the landscape and co-develop a Discipline-Specific Data and Software Management Framework. The degree of scientific impact that could be achieved by adoption of this framework is summarized in Geoscience Advances.

Hydrology Community Readiness: The hydrology disciplinary communities within both AGU and EGU are the largest, and both have established hierarchy, working groups, and significant member participation. Researchers from both AGU and EGU have communicated the desire to establish these leading practices and requested support.

Ocean Science Community Readiness: The ocean science community has a long history of data sharing, in part due to the inherent interdisciplinary nature of oceanographic research driving a strong need to share data across the subdisciplines (i.e., biological, chemical, physical and geological oceanography) to answer complex process and system questions. But, when coupled with the high cost and effort of sea-going research, there is great incentive to share and reuse data as much as possible. However, in spite of a comparatively strong willingness to share, data interoperability remains a challenge. Oceanographic data are not born FAIR and the continuing evolution of novel data types from new sensors creates additional challenges for integration efforts (Tanhua et al., 2019). Consequently, data infrastructures have evolved to support specialized sub-disciplines within this community and are now pushing the field of ocean informatics through use of semantic technologies and standardized metadata (Buttigieg, 2024).

Recently, the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development has elevated the need for Open and FAIR data to solve grand challenges for ocean research (UNESCO-IOC, 2023), specifically the UN Sustainable Development Goal No 14 (U.N. Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023). Many concerted efforts in marine data interoperability have been launched internationally in the marine observing communities, where collaborations across mature ocean observing systems have been successful in providing wide discovery and access for marine data (e.g., SeaDataNet, EMODNet, IMOS, refs). However, achieving interoperability remains one of the remaining challenges, despite globally accessible resources such as Ocean Best Practices (Perlman et al., 2019). Further collaboration across these systems is now occurring in international venues by societies and international organizations such as AGU, EGU, TOS, ASLO, IODE, and CODATA, convening the oceanographic community on data sharing practices and resources; raising awareness and building consensus (Buttigieg, 2024). This high degree of awareness and understanding of the problem confirms community readiness for researcher-level

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

support to help improve data management, sharing, and ultimately interoperability to support advancing new oceanographic research.

Seismology Community Readiness: The seismological science community has been at the forefront of efforts to “FAIRify” scientific data for nearly four decades (Romanowicz & Dziewonski, 1986). Driven by collaborative regional-, national-, continent- and global-scale efforts to deploy seismometers and related instruments for broad science applications, and enhance the sharing of collected data, the community has already coalesced on several metadata and data standards (Pedersen et al., in press). Unique among many of its disciplinary peers, it has an international governing body for these standards: the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN), which has enabled establishment of one of the best globally standardised networks of geoscientific data. Nevertheless, many of these standards and leading practices were developed prior to the FAIR principles and few enable the explicit machine-actionable requirements of FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Further, these standards are specific to the seismology community, and interdisciplinary data merging is extremely difficult. With increasing uptake of AI and ML tools, the community is poised to take advantage of these new technologies, but the current standards are not sufficiently rigorous, particularly with respect to vocabularies to enable machine-to-machine data aggregation and analysis. Towards this end, there is a coalescence of disciplinary data experts focused on addressing these challenges (Haslinger et al., 2025; Pedersen et al., in press). The proposed work will amplify established FDSN standardization efforts by enhancing standards to support machine-actionable data, in particular making discipline-specific vocabularies fully FAIR compliant, consolidating key discipline leadership and researcher champions who will catalyze dissemination and adoption.

7. Project Management Plan

7.1 Project Team Each of the steps in the project plan will be co-led and managed by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia; assisted by the Network Collaborator Committee. The proposed work, requiring broad participation from across the research ecosystem, benefits from the Co-PI’s different perspectives. The team embodies the vision of a future Open Science Ecosystem that elevates the work of the researcher with the infrastructure and tools necessary to address convergent concerns of humanity that are being thwarted by poorly managed research assets such as data, software, and physical samples.

Shelley Stall is a recognized expert in international Open Science community networks with deep journal and publisher connections through her AGU affiliation and as a co-chair for the Coalition on Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS). Shelley works closely with AGU Section leaders and is developing strong connections to EGU Divisions leaders. Shelley will ensure that the needed people are invited to participate, solidifying the success of this work. Shelley serves as AGU’s Vice President of Open Science Leadership, and a certified Project Management Professional (PMP) (cert ID 1341027).

Danie Kinkade brings insights into the curation and publication of heterogeneous geoscience research outputs through her leadership of a longstanding trustworthy NSF disciplinary repository serving the ocean ecology community. The Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO) fully implements FAIR Principles, linking its data catalog to related data providers such as NIH, SESAR Physical Sample repository, PANGEA, etc., and provides the tools to explore their data holdings. Danie is a thought leader in the disciplinary repository community, recently moved into the position of past-president for the AGU Informatics Section with the role of mentor to the current executive team.

Natalie Raia is an early-career boundary spanner and data-savvy expert who bridges research data management, informatics solutions, and real-world application with geophysical researchers. Raia actively co-chairs (with Co-PI Kinkade) an international Research Data Alliance working group bringing

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

together data repository and publisher stakeholders towards creation of recommendations for improving data publication workflows. Raia brings an aptitude for working with researchers across disciplines, embodied by her recent interdisciplinary work mapping the Quaternary data resource ecosystem as part of the NSF FAIROS Research Coordination Network, “Ethical Open Science for Past Global Change Data.”

The PI team will meet regularly (virtually and during in-person meetings of opportunity) to ensure timely execution of activities and mitigate emerging issues and risks. The PIs will organize and facilitate community stakeholder meetings, prepare the Framework, and ensure its tuning to each discipline. A detailed list of organizations represented by the PI team and Network Collaborator Committee along with the Letters of Collaboration are available in the supplementary files. Travel is planned for meetings where researchers from the targeted disciplines will be attending to support discussion and awareness building (e.g., AGU, EGU) as well as participating in international Open Science experts conferences (RDA).

The project will employ multiple collaborative open communication and content management strategies including Google suite for preliminary documents and scratch space, and Github for mature content and website development. Documents and related content will be shared with appropriate collaborators and target community members. Final products will be published in relevant open venues (see Data Management Plan).

7.2 Network Collaborator Committee: This work will be assisted by a Network Collaborator Committee (8 members; Table 1) representing repository and research community stakeholders for the selected disciplines. These individuals are leaders in their representative communities and possess a broad geoscience network necessary to complete this work. These leaders also will bring grounding to the work, informing the design of the framework and facilitating conversations with the disciplinary community members convened during the workshops to assist these communities in designing the long-term, focused plan for governing and updating the framework. The Network Collaborator Committee will be expected to socialize this work and help engage their respective networks (see individual and organizational letters of support in supplemental materials).

Organization	Discipline	Representative
World Data System/Ocean Networks Canada	Cross-Disciplinary	Reyna Jenkyns, Associate Director, International Technology Office
Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science (CUASHI)	Hydrology	Jordan Reed, Executive Director
Internet of Water	Hydrology	Kyle Onda, Director Internet of Water, Center for Geospatial Solutions
International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange	Oceans	Peter Pissierssons, Head, IOC Project Office
British Oceanographic Data Center	Oceans	Justin Buck, Senior Data Scientist, Marine Autonomous and Robotics Data Systems
Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	Oceans	Pier Luigi Buttigieg, Senior Data Scientist; Chair, Ocean Data and Information System Project of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO
Australian National University,	Cross-Disciplinary, Seismology	Lesley Wyborn, Honorary Professor, Research School of Earth Sciences
Université Grenoble-Alpes	Seismology	Helle Pedersen, Professor Dr., ISTerre

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

Table 1. Composition of Network Collaborator Committee, indicating the organization and discipline represented, and the confirmed invited representative.

7.3 Discipline Participants

Below we outline the methodology to be applied for each discipline. The method leverages a core framework model and is grounded in participatory action. Groups of community members to be engaged are defined as follows:

Discipline Leadership: AGU section leadership, EGU division leadership, Editors-in-Chief for disciplinary journals

Discipline Liaisons: These individuals represent disciplinary-experts who liaise with AGU Informatics Section/EGU Earth and Space Sciences Informatics (ESSI) Division, modeled after the current EGU ESSI Division Science Officers, that bridge topics related to informatics and their assigned scientific division. AGU Informatics, as part of supporting this work, will establish a similar role. This role is envisaged to be filled by early-career researchers, and the position fully codified and sustained as a permanent AGU Informatics leadership position beyond the grant.

Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Repositories: For each discipline focus area, we have secured Letters of Collaboration from key discipline repositories, coordinating their participation. Should we discover a repository not previously included, we will invite them to also participate.

Researchers: Key interested researchers will be identified through the networks of the Discipline Leadership and liaisons and via AGU and EGU community communication avenues. Researchers are integral to grounding the framework (ensuring it is reasonable) and in championing adoption. This includes collaboration with FAIR RCN focused on Instrument PIDs, and Ixchel Faniel, prominent researcher in the necessary context for data to be reused.

Our work follows an organizational change management approach effective for research communities prioritizing open communication, strong stakeholder engagement, evidence-based decision making. We are focusing on the alignment of new practices and existing scientific norms, including fostering a culture of collaboration and continuous learning to ensure researchers readily adopt and integrate new practices, processes, or systems while maintaining their research integrity (Hubbart, 2023; Rousseau & ten Have, 2022).

7.4 Confidence in Success: The AGU's Open Science Leadership (OSL) team has been working with AGU Section leadership and EGU Division leadership for the last two years socializing the activities described in this proposal. These conversations have been positive, with great interest in the intent to support. In 2024, AGU's OSL team took those conversations to the next level convening town halls at both EGU24 and AGU24 for the hydrology discipline. Initial discipline leadership and repositories were identified, and the team gained the backing of section leadership and the Editor-in-chief of the Water Resources Research (WRR), an AGU journal. Engaging both AGU and EGU community members is important for long-term success in co-developing discipline-specific leading practices that originate in and are endorsed and implemented by international communities. These practices need to be co-developed with ongoing management originating from the discipline community. Such practices must be international; therefore, engaging both AGU and EGU community members is important for long-term success. This work will be positioned in a neutral space where all societies and participants feel their contributions are meaningful.

7.5 Project Outcomes

Tool: Framework Toolkit, with implementation guidance, for additional disciplines to implement that are demonstrating community readiness.

Quantitative for Hydrology, Oceans, and Seismology:

1. A Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Management Framework.

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

2. A vetted set of leading practices that are reviewed, approved, and mapped to the framework.
3. A neutrally-branded web platform where community members can easily locate trusted data and digital object management leading practices with the context to apply the information.

Qualitative for Hydrology, Oceans, and Seismology:

Engaged Discipline Leadership, Discipline Liaisons, and researchers that support and use the vetted resources, monitor for new leading practices, and sustain the framework with updated content.

7.6 Project Metrics

- The project will conduct two short discipline-centric surveys; one before and one after the creation of the framework (allowing enough time for socialization and adoption) soliciting confidence levels of researchers in finding and using resources on community leading practices, standards and formats that enable them to share their data. These results will be published along with related project results.
- The project will report on stakeholder partnerships sustained over the duration of the performance period via participation of the discipline-specific journals and repositories such that a core number are represented, agreement to endorse the content, adopt the materials, influence the community, and help lead the implementation.
- Discipline-relevant AGU Sections and EGU Divisions participate and agree to review the materials, provide feedback, and promote adoption.
- Number of researchers engaging the recommendations and resources for each discipline via views of materials from the hosting website.

8.0 Project Activities

8.1 Overarching Timeline

Below we outline a high-level timeline of the period of performance (Table 2). This is followed by a detailed timeline of project activities in Section 8.3.

Activity / Month	Y1 Q1	Y1 Q2	Y1 Q3	Y1 Q4	Y2 Q1	Y2 Q2	Y2 Q3	Y2 Q4	
Project Plan									
8.2 Engage Network Collaborator Committee									
8.3 Collaborate with Each Discipline									
Discipline 1: Hydrology					Sustainment				
Discipline 2: Oceans					Sustainment				
Discipline 3: Seismology									Sustain
8.4 Publish Framework Toolkit and Conduct Train-the-Discipline Events									

Table 2. Timeline showing key project tasks over the period of performance. Dark blue indicates the duration of project activities and light blue indicates sustainment phases of the work.

8.2 Engage Network Collaborator Committee (Month 1)

The Network Collaborator Committee consists of leaders within existing international organizations focused on research data and the three target disciplines. In the first month of Year 1, the co-PI's will meet with the Network Collaborator Committee to kick off the work, setting the vision for the next two years of work and soliciting feedback, questions, and ideas. The Network Collaborator Committee will be kept apprised of all significant milestones and invited to participate in as much of the collaborative process as they have interest, expertise, and time. Individual members will be activated at key moments to reach out into their network to identify stakeholders to bring in ongoing framework development, and, eventually, to support dissemination and adoption.

8.3 Collaborate with Each Discipline: Below we outline a timeline of the steps (Table 3). This is followed by a detailed timeline of project activities in Section 8.3.

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

Step 1: Gather the Components for Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Management Framework (1 Month)

In preparation for engaging with a discipline, project Co-PI's will conduct a structured literature review of existing leading practices, data and metadata standards, community norms, available data resources, and disciplinary-relevant journals, to be assembled into a preliminary Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Management Framework. This review will be time bound, and likely not comprehensive, providing a starting point for participatory community work achieved in Step 2. Co-PI's will meet with the Network Collaborator Committee to review the outcomes of this initial step and receive feedback.

Activity / Month	Y1 Q1	Y1 Q2	Y1 Q3	Y1 Q4
<i>For Each Discipline</i>				
Step 1: Gather the Components for Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Management Framework				
Step 2: Co-Create and Refine Framework Through a Participatory Approach				
Step 3: Review, Publish, Disseminate, Socialize, Adopt				Ongoing
Step 4: Governance, Sustain, and Improve				Ongoing

Table 3. Timeline showing key project tasks over the period of performance. Dark orange indicates the duration of each step and light orange indicates ongoing activities to be sustained by each discipline beyond the performance period, under the governance structure and mechanisms co-developed over the course of this project.

Step 2: Co-Create and Refine Framework Through a Participatory Approach (3 Months)

Co-convene Research Leadership Workshop: Engage the appropriate Discipline Leadership and Discipline Liaisons in an initial virtual “Researcher Leadership Workshop” (~10 people) to introduce the project goals, vision, and framework. Network Collaborator Committee members will be invited to attend this workshop, and may speak to their perspectives on the value-proposition and vision for the work.

Co-identify Discipline-Specific Leading Practices: During the workshop, Discipline Leadership and Discipline Liaisons will (1) edit, update, and further refine the framework document, and (2) identify people and groups to engage in a larger virtual “Disciplinary Community Workshop” (~30 people).

Co-convene Discipline Workshop with Leadership: Once Discipline Leaders and Liaisons are satisfied with the status of the framework, a larger virtual Disciplinary Community Workshop will be convened. The workshop will bring in disciplinary repository leaders, researchers, and organizations for continued assessment and refinement of the framework.

Workshop Participant Iterative Comment and Review: Following the workshop the draft framework and leading practices will be open for review and comment by the Discipline Leadership and Workshop Participants. Comments will be addressed and any requests for updates reviewed with the Discipline Leadership as needed.

Vetting Process for Potential Leading Practices: The process for vetting by a community needs to be defined to ensure proper agreement and community support. The co-PIs will recommend a process for each type of framework component to assess how well it meets the needs of the Open Science Ecosystem. It is important that the discipline community makes the determination on what components to include in the framework. These community-specific leading practices support researchers in responding to PAPPG and Division level funding, guiding their compliance with the Data Management and Sharing Plan elements, driving further adoption of these resources.

Step 3: Review, Publish, Disseminate, Socialize, Adopt (6 Months)

Review: Provide opportunity for the broader community to give feedback and comment. Work with Discipline Leadership and workshop participants to address all comments. Depending on the number of comments, there may need to be more than one interaction of review.

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries:
Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

Publish, Disseminate across Network, and Socialize: Publish leading practices for both ease of discovery, use, version control, and citation.

Launch web platform to host framework and leading practice content: The finalized (and updated) framework and practices will be hosted on a GitHub website, a neutral location, for all discipline community members to search and discover their discipline's agreed upon leading practices. The content will be indexed and openly licensed. Should existing community-preferred content hosting resources be available, partnership will be explored.

Adopt (Ongoing): Discipline Leadership, Workshop Participants, their organizations and networks are encouraged to adopt the recommended practices identified in the framework. They can encourage this through awareness workshops, hackathons, and demonstrations. The Co-PIs will collaborate with the Discipline Leadership to prepare a plan that will leverage existing discipline gatherings, and meetings to help encourage adoption across the community. The intent is for this work to be led by the Discipline Leadership and codified in the work of the AGU Sections and EGU Divisions.

Step 4: Governance, Sustain, and Improve (5 Months)

Governance: As noted above, the Discipline Leadership will be engaging the question on the best type of governance necessary for the ongoing management of the discipline framework and leading practices, including periodic review and update of the web platform (with ongoing support from AGU). It is possible there already exists a mechanism to do this. For instance, some of AGU's Sections include an EGU Liaison. We will collect recommendations with the intent on using an existing governance mechanism, if one exists. If one does not exist the information provided in Step 2 will inform possible options to pursue.

Sustain: Following the finalization and publication of the first version of the discipline framework and practices, the Discipline Leadership will reconvene to review any newly identified practices, feedback, or other concerns.

Improve (Ongoing): The co-PIs will conduct a survey at the end of each workshop/event and experience on the web platform, updated the web platform content, and update the Toolkit Framework. Information from the survey responses will be aggregated and applied to the process, content, and framework improving the experience for the next discipline as well as support ongoing management of the materials.

8.4 Publish Framework Toolkit and Conduct Train-the-Discipline Events

The Framework Toolkit will be designed to **facilitate adoption of Discipline-Specific Leading Practices for Data & Digital Object Management**. The Framework Toolkit, with application guidance, for additional disciplines to implement that are demonstrating community readiness, will be continually updated during the project. In the last quarter of the grant period, final updates will be made, and a Train-the-Discipline event will be held. In this workshop we will 1) request participants to prepare a list of their known data resources; 2) review the purpose and content of the Framework Toolkit, 3) Practice applying a Vetting Process to the resources they identified, and 4) discuss implementing governance, network dissemination, and sustainment. The Framework Toolkit includes: the framework template, type of participants/roles to invite, guidelines for decision making process, basic governance to have in place, examples of working frameworks.

9. Broader Impacts

This project will bring together key international discipline leadership, repositories, journal editors, and researchers focused on creating awareness and building capacity in FAIR and Open research practices within the geosciences. The result of which will facilitate a paradigm shift in the research lifecycle by actively recommending the integration of data sharing and repository collaboration early and throughout the lifecycle. It will form novel and sustainable partnerships between researchers, research cyberinfrastructure, and journal editors to improve the **effectiveness and value** of Open Science practices

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

and bring clarity to currently disparate data publication policies and requirements. Project outcomes and a collaborative approach to awareness and adoption will lower barriers, improve research data management and sharing practices, and foster a future data-savvy research workforce in alignment with NSF and other governmental Open Science strategies. The result of which will directly enable critical geoscience research to move forward where it is currently hindered by the lack of awareness and quality of existing data sources. The project will support an early career geoscience data professional by providing valued opportunities in Open Science leadership. Resulting products will be made open and shared broadly to allow other disciplines to replicate this approach, further amplifying the impact of this work.

10. Geoscience Advancement

We are entering into a “FAIR data crisis” where valuable data are increasingly “lost” to un-FAIR and siloed archival locations (Vrouwenvelder & Stall, 2024). **Not only are the goals of funder and journal data sharing requirements going unrealized, but we risk moving backwards. Instead of achieving discoverable, interoperable, and reusable data, they are increasingly siloed, and un-FAIRly.** Researchers, particularly producers of high-value, long-tail data, are unknowingly left behind because the impacts of this “FAIR data crisis” are going unrecognized in the short term. This is due to the fact that although they produce high-value data, their research questions continue to be shaped by the quality and availability of known and reusable data. To unleash transformative research of the future, FAIR data, vetted disciplinary-specific data sharing frameworks are non-negotiable.

Each of the target disciplines was chosen based on the substantial but disparate corpus of existing resources, a demonstrated receptiveness to improve FAIR and Open data practices, and a demonstrated need for the type of work proposed here (Section 6). Without the proposed work, there will be no progress toward reducing the “time to science”, nor any advancement in unlocking new interdisciplinary scientific discoveries essential for addressing the grand challenges society will face in the coming decade and beyond. In essence, the status quo will remain unchanged.

The potential benefits and impacts of supporting researchers in their access and use of community practices, and FAIR, trustworthy repositories can be demonstrated by the current research that is occurring at great effort and in spite of a dearth of well-described, interoperable data sources. One such example in oceanography is the Synthesis Product for Ocean Time Series (SPOT, Lange et al., 2024); a comprehensive data synthesis of global ocean biogeochemical data from twelve disparate international ship-based time series databases. This work enabled improved understanding of the variability in ocean biogeochemistry, broadening our view of ocean processes and systems, and maximizing the return on our continued investment in ocean observations. However, the data processing was an extremely labor-intensive, manual process comprising most of the author’s PhD work, and highlights the value of metadata standards and community practices in facilitating downstream reuse of geoscience data. Notably, this effort was used as a pilot to assess feasibility of using highly-valued, but currently inoperable data sources. It built consensus across this community through collaborations with individual research programs, socializing and adopting standardized procedures and practices, thereby advancing the community toward future interoperability (Lange et al., 2024). The proposed work will catalyze and shine light on the types of efforts described above as the frameworks are co-created with the three target disciplines.

11. Open Science Alignment

The proposed work will build a sustainable community resource within each of the three disciplines that serves to drive their community toward a shared vision of common data (and other digital objects) resources, methods and tools that are grounded in Open Science and FAIR data principles. This will be a fundamental transformation for Hydrology, Oceans, and Seismology.

Project Description

GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities

The process of discipline-specific framework development will coalesce existing community resources and provide an informal gap analysis for each discipline to identify areas for development of leading practices (e.g., uptake of PIDs), vocabularies, and integration of standards. The vetting process includes open science practitioners to provide a steady influence on the long-term value of data as an asset and the overall need for better data management and preservation methods and protocols. Discipline Leadership and Liaisons, through adoption and awareness efforts, help shape the path that will benefit broader science goals:

1. Community resources identified in partnership with respective members (e.g., demonstrating that a discipline repository is a preferred place to discover needed data and preferable to a literature review).
2. Interoperable data that are machine-actionable supporting discovery, trust, and reuse; minimizing the burden of data wrangling and cleaning for reuse.
3. A discipline-specific leadership that intentionally fosters skills development in data management, Open Science, and FAIR data practices within their own communities.

Framework dissemination and socialization will lower a key barrier to the realization of the value of Open Science practices by putting community-vetted resources at the heart of where researchers share their research and connect to their colleagues - society communities and meetings.

12. Results from Prior

Stall: NSF 2025364, **PIs:** S. Stall, **10/01/2020 – 09/30/2024, \$623,794.** *Accelerating Open and FAIR Data Practices Across the Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences: A Pilot with the NSF to Support Public Access to Research Data.* **Intellectual Merit:** This work ensured data and software citation are correctly coded and managed in the publication workflow, with a 95% AGU improvement by 2024; created author guidance for data and software deposition and citation (4K views, 3K downloads) in papers; developed author guidance for citing software, Jupyter Notebooks and R Markdown (combined 2.5K + views, 1.2K downloads); and introduced the concept of “Digital Presence” leveraging ORCID profiles to optimize the discovery of PI digital products (1K views, 667 downloads). Comprehensive AGU author guidance is available to all societies, and CHORUS provided NSF with access to papers associated with grants, including data links. Outreach activities were provided during AGU’s Open Science and Data Help Desk, workshops at scientific meetings, journal society meetings, and the repository communities. **Broader Impacts:** This work accelerated culture change and practices to allow tracking of and credit for data by identifying actionable solutions for making data citations machine-actionable properly and laid a foundation that can be scaled across NSF and other agencies, and across publishers in other disciplines. **Products and Publications:** See References Cited Section, “Shelley Stall, Results from Prior Work Publications for NSF 2025364, Accelerating Open and FAIR Data Practices Across the Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences: A Pilot with the NSF to Support Public Access to Research Data”.

Kinkade: NSF OCE-2421145 - **PIs:** D. Kinkade, A. Shepherd; 9/1/24- 8/31/29; \$11,724,978. *BCO-DMO: Streamlining the Ocean Data Life Cycle to Advance Interdisciplinary Research and Education.* **Intellectual Merit:** This grant is the core funding for the BCO-DMO office, and led to the ingestion and serving of over 6,500 varied datasets from NSF funded projects. BCO-DMO also actively contributes to informatics and data management science and is broadly considered a leader in this effort. **Broader Impact:** Data from BCO-DMO is widely used globally for research and education. BCO-DMO’s website has been accessed from 183 countries worldwide and is used as a teaching tool for (under)graduate classes at several US academic institutions. **Products and Publications:** BCO-DMO’s database and website; Wiebe et al., 2015; Wiebe and Allison, 2015, Kinkade and Shepherd, 2022.

Natalie Raia: This Co-PI has not previously served as PI or co-PI on any NSF awards.